

WAYS OF INTRODUCING CHILDREN TO NATURE AT THE "ILM FAN AND NATURE" CENTER IN PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Acquaintance with nature is an inexhaustible source of spiritual enrichment of a person, we know that the infinite color world of nature arouses great interest in children, encourages them to play, work, and create art. However, when children communicate with nature independently, they cannot understand everything correctly, their relationship with plants and animals is not always formed correctly. In order to introduce the child to the natural world, to show its objects and phenomena correctly, it is necessary to direct them to understand the process of perception of nature. Treating nature with caution and care, when children have at least basic knowledge about it - when they learn simple methods of growing plants, caring for animals, can be seen in their ability to express the feeling of beauty. First of all, knowledge of nature develops the thinking of entering into the cause-and-effect relationships between objects and events and helps to form a scientific worldview. Children are always in contact with nature in one form or another. Green forests and meadows, flowers and butterflies, beetles, birds, animals, moving clouds, falling snowflakes, streams, even puddles after a summer rain - all this attracts children's attention. , makes them happy. At the same time, it creates the ground for mental development.

Introduction to nature in preschool educational organizations is carried out in various forms: in the activity center "Science and Nature", practical activities,

excursions, everyday life, observations (during walks), conversations, and work. Preschool education organization "Ilk Cadam" strives to create the necessary conditions for each child, taking into account his abilities, opportunities, mental and physical conditions, taking into account the uniqueness and uniqueness of each child's personality, based on the State curriculum. to support their interests and needs, allows children to implement the individual approach of pedagogues in the educational process. Educational activities in the field of "Developing the process of knowing" are based on the annual thematic plan given in the State curriculum "First Step" based on the themes of the month and the themes of the week, it is conducted in the activity center called "Science and Nature" and in various activities during the day. The work of the following development centers will be organized according to the topics of the week within the monthly topics:

1. *"Language and speech" center.*
2. *"Building, design and mathematics" center*
3. *"Art" center*
4. *"Science and nature" center*
5. *Center "Role-playing games and dramatization"*

Mainly, in the activity center called "Science and Nature", educational processes are conducted on weekly topics of introduction to nature. Also, in other activities of the center and in other parts of the day, the educator pays attention to the concepts and knowledge of the children and tries to develop them when they consistently express their thoughts about nature and draw conclusions, and when they express their observations about the environment. does. Activities at the center should be interesting, solve the set goals and tasks, educational materials and play equipment should be suitable for the age of the children of the group, be safe and arouse their interest. The tasks and tasks at the center should be understandable to the children. Each center is prepared and equipped at the beginning of the week. During the work of the center, the educator observes the knowledge, skills, and abilities of the children, and pays attention to how

interesting, understandable and easy the recommended materials are for the children. If necessary, the educator completes or changes educational materials. Based on the results of the observation, the educator plans to work individually with the child and his parents to introduce him to nature.

At the end of every week, the educator analyzes the activities of children in the field of nature introduction, learns what the children have learned, what they want to know, observes the interests and needs of each child, their interaction with adults and peers, and concludes. At the same time, the materials are thoroughly analyzed to what extent they are interesting and literate, whether the set goal has been achieved or not. After that, preparations are made for the next week.

Thus, properly organized work in development centers allows each child to engage in activities that he likes, to test his strength and abilities, to work together with adults and peers, to have various experiences. allows for transfer and analysis, which is the basis of developmental education.

In practical activities, the educator uses viewing pictures, reading works of art, showing stories, slides and motion pictures, and work in nature. Children apply the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in work and games.

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